

Managing National Social Investment Programmes for Economic Sustainability and Educational Development in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated managing national social investment programmes and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State, Nigeria. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlation design with a population of 313 principals in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample consisted all the 313 principals using census sampling technique. The instruments for data collection are Managing National Social Investment Programmes Questionnaire and Economic Sustainability in Education Questionnaire. The reliability was determined using Cronbach Method. The following reliability indexes are: .83 for Managing National Social Investment Programmes and .86 for Economic Sustainability in Education accordingly. Out of 313 copies of questionnaire administered, 304 were properly filled and retrieved which represented 96% success rate. The research questions were answered using simple regression while the hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with simple regression at 0.05 level of significant. The findings among others revealed that national cash transfer programme predicted economic sustainability by 22.9% and there is a significant prediction between national cash transfer programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. The study concluded that all the components of managing national social investment programmes which are considered in this study has a positive prediction to economic sustainability in education in Rivers State with different determinism.

Keywords: *Social, Investment, Economic, Sustainability.*

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Introduction

Africa is one of the poorest continents of the world in terms of economic viability and development and Nigeria which is regarded as the giant of Africa has been labelled with wide spread poverty across the different states with about half of its citizens in the poverty line (Iheonu & Urama, 2019). This figure which is still counting has

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compelled the government to initiate different programmes that can help to cushion the effects of economic hardship and reduce the level of poverty among the citizens. This is because the economic independence of the citizens has a multiplier effect on national growth and development.

In Nigeria, the poverty rate among those in the low and middle income level has been rising as a result of several economic and social crises that have affected the country. There have been multiple cases of economic recession in the last six years and this is in addition to social problems such as civil protest, communal clashes and increasing social vices which has further impoverished the masses. This development has led to different calls and agitation from concerned citizens and institutions on the need to devise ways of instilling true economic sustainability programmes especially among the citizens at the grass root so as to make them self-reliant and this has contributed to the introduction of several economic programmes targeted at turning the existing economic tide.

Economic Sustainability in Education

Economic sustainability involves providing means of economic survival for the present generation on a continuous basis without jeopardizing the economic survival of the future generation. It also involves putting measures in place to ensure the economic independence of the present generation. Namarong (2012) noted that economic independence is the ability to own and control wealth as well as local ownership of resources and means of production. An economically independent citizen is able to meet his or her immediate needs as well as contribute to the growth and development of their immediate environment and this forms part of the intention of the social investment programme initiated by the Federal Government for youths and women across the different states of the federation including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). This effort is what guarantees true economic sustainability. It is expected that this kind of programme will enable the beneficiaries to be able to procure basic factors of production which will enable them go into production of goods or rendering of service at their level. This will help to reduce the level of economic dependence on the government and other family members and will rather enable these individuals contribute in their little quota to their immediate environment economically.

National Social Investment Programme

The National Social Investment Program of Nigeria is a social welfare initiative launched by the federal government of Nigeria in 2015 (WikiMili, 2025). The program, overseen by the National Social Investment Office, aims to promote equitable resource distribution to vulnerable populations, such as children, youth, and women. The National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) in Nigeria is composed of four main components: the National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP), the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP), the Job Creation and Youth Empowerment (N-Power), and the National Cash Transfer Programme (NCTP) (Idoko, & Udentia, 2023). These programs aim to alleviate poverty, improve economic well-being, and promote inclusiveness.

The National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) was conceived in Nigeria in 2015 and got implemented in 2016. The State House, Abuja (2020) noted that this programme is a social welfare initiative of the Federal Government of Nigeria under the leadership of President Muhammadu Buhari under the direction of the National Social Investment Office with the intention of ensuring an equitable distribution of

available resources to the vulnerable populations especially children, youths, and women. There are several intervention programmes captured in the scheme which included the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) which is for poorest households, the home grown school feeding programme designed for primary school pupils, the Government Entrepreneurship and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) designed for widows and market women and the N-Power for unemployed graduates (Abada & Omeh, 2019; Ugo & Olewe, 2018:4). These programmes were initiated to reduce the level of poverty and improve on the economic independence of beneficiaries.

National Cash Transfer Programme (NCTP)

This program provides cash transfers to the poor and vulnerable, conditional on fulfilling co-responsibilities, to support their basic needs and enhance their standard of living. On their part, Ugo and Olewe (2018:6) stated that “the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) programme exist in the form of grants given to specifically identified poor household with a condition attached to it that they must engage in investments. Similarly, Taylor and Ogbogu (2016:40) asserted that “the school feeding is simply the provision of food to children through schools”. However, there are other beneficiaries of this programme which includes cook who prepare the meals for these children and the farmers who are engaged to grow the raw products that will be handed to the cooks and prepared for the pupils. These cooks and farmers also benefit from the value chain of the National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP). This initiative also contributes to the creation of employment for these engaged workers.

Job Creation and Youth Empowerment (N-Power)

N-Power offers young Nigerians job training, education, and a monthly stipend, with various sub-programs like N-Teach, N-Agro, and N-Health, as well as programs like N-Power Knowledge and N-Power Build. Similarly, Ugo and Olewe (2018) stated that “the N-power programme is a social intervention policy made by the federal government to provide job opportunities for the teaming unemployed youths in Nigeria”. The N-power programme covers different employment opportunities for both graduates and non-graduates for a period of 24 months and three months respectively. The graduates are provided time bound empowerment in the form of N-Teach, N-Agric, N-Health, N-Tax while the non-graduate beneficiaries are provided opportunity to learn skills in programmes such as N-Tech Hardware, N-Tech Software among others.

Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP)

GEEP is a micro-lending initiative that provides loans to traders, artisans, young entrepreneurs, farmers, and women, particularly. These loans are intended to help businesses, with a focus on those in need of a financial boost. Akujuru (2019) also added that the Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) which included Market Moni and Trader Moni programmes is an empowerment programme to enable petty traders to boost their businesses. These programmes were targeted at providing skills and job oppourtunity for its beneficiaries to both reduce the level of poverty and promote economic sustainability and independence among the citizens.

Since the introduction of the social investment programme in Nigeria, several studies have been carried out to determine its level of implementation and effects. One of such studies was carried out by Gbaranbiri (2023) focusing on national social investment programme (NSIP) and sustainable poverty reduction in Nigeria focusing on challenges and prospects (Gbaranbiri, 2023). It was revealed in the study that the

programmes suffered as a result of the lack of funding and it was also reported that only 300billion out of the 1.5trillion ear marked for the 2016 and 2017 appropriation was actually released (Onah & Olise, 2019). Furthermore, Onyishi and Ogbu (2019) also conducted a study on the social intervention programmes and rural development in Nigeria with emphasis on a study of federal government's trader-moni initiative. The finding revealed that beneficiaries of the GEEP contributed to policy formulation indirectly through their various associations.

Furthermore, Bisong (2019) also conducted a study on the impact assessment of the n-power scheme in southern senatorial district of Cross River State and the study showed that there was a positive significant relationship between the N-power scheme and economic wellbeing as well as job skill enhancement and employment generation. Also, Ugo (2018) carried out an assessment of implementation of social intervention policies in Nigeria with a survey of Economic Planning Commission and Ministry of Human Capital Development and Poverty Reduction in Enugu State and his finding was that problems like institutional capacity; poor coordination and supervision; poor service delivery as well as infrastructure, low value of the cash transfers also hindered the effectiveness of the objectives of the cash transfer programme (Ugo, & Olewe, 2018).

National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP)

This program focuses on providing school meals to children, aiming to increase school enrolment, reduce malnutrition, and empower community women as cooks while supporting local farmers. Similarly, Karisa and Orodho (2014) carried out a related study by assessing the home grown school feeding programme (HGSFP) theory in Kinango Sub-County, Kwale County, Kenya and their finding was that the HGSFP did not directly benefit the local community as was envisaged because most of the people supplying food to the school do not reside close to the school but instead operated from other centers. Similarly, farmers participating in the HGSFP were constrained by low yields because of lack of modern agricultural production techniques and stringent procurement procedures (Orodho, & Karisa, 2014). There was also the problem of erratic disbursement of the funds meant for the project. Furthermore, Alabede et al., (2020) also assessed the impact of national home grown school feeding programme on the academic performance of pupils in selected primary schools, Orire Local Government, Oyo State and they found out that the programme contributed to improved academic performance and regularity among students in the study area.

In a related dimension, Azubuike and Mbah, (2019) investigated the challenges of child nutrition by analysis the school feeding programmes (SFP) in South Eastern Nigeria and its finding showed that 84.0% of the teachers graded the school feeding program as being average, 36.7% of the caterers reported cases of inadequate supply of food stuffs and 23.3% said there was problem of regular hike in food prices and inadequate storage facilities which hindered the programme (Azubuike, & Mbah, 2010). Supporting this study, Awojobi (2019) also conducted a systematic review of the impact of Ghana's school feeding programme on educational and nutritional outcomes and the outcome of the study showed that despite the good objectives of the programme, it was bedevilled by several challenges.

The Social Investment Programmes in Nigeria appear to have been implemented in a hurry without recourse to how it will be managed and the objectives it intends to achieve. This is because the commitment to the programme in terms of financing, logistics, training has not been able to measure up with the effort of other countries in

the same set of programmes. These programmes no doubt have the capacity of bring about a national transformation in the country but this is subject to the level of commitment that will be shown by relevant stakeholders.

So far, the Social Investment Programmes remains a national programme with only some states buying into the idea by considering some of the programmes at the state level. Some states are also yet to consider any of these programmes because it is already being managed by the Federal Government. However, it is important to note that the benefits of these programmes cannot be sustainable without the support of the state and local government. Therefore, states in Nigeria need to give these programmes maximum support in cash or in kind as the programme is all about the well-being of members of the public in these states.

Statement of the Problem

The social investment programme in Nigeria was initiated with the intention of improving on the social and economic well-being of unemployed youths and women who are socially and economically vulnerable in the country. Despite the laudable objectives of the programmes outlined, very few persons have benefitted from the programme with some qualified and others not so qualified to be part of the programme. It is therefore worrisome to note if the method of sensitization adopted in the programmes make it easy for the real target group to be reached. Similarly, the economic effects of the various programmes appear not to have made so much progress given the increasing level of poverty among the populace. Therefore, the researcher is bothered whether managing national social investment programmes could predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The aim of the study investigated managing national social investment programmes and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State, Nigeria. The objectives sought to:

1. investigate the extent **national cash transfer programme** predicts economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
2. find out the extent **job creation programme** predicts economic sustainability in education in Rivers State
3. ascertain the extent **empowerment programme** predicts economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
4. identify the extent **national home-grown school feeding programme** predicts economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study;

1. To what extent does **national cash transfer programme** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does **job creation programme** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does **empowerment programme** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

4. To what extent does **national home-grown school feeding programme** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance in this study

1. **National cash transfer programme does not significantly** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
2. **Job creation programme does not significantly** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
3. **Empowerment programme does not significantly** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
4. **National home-grown school feeding programme does not significantly** predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Methodology

The study adopted correlation design. The population of the study comprised all the 313 principals in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample consisted all the 313 principals in secondary schools using census sampling technique. The instruments for data collection are Managing National Social Investment Programmes Questionnaire (MNSIPQ) and Economic Sustainability in Education Questionnaire (ESEQ). The instrument were guided by 40 items structured on a modified four point Likert scale of Very High Extent -4points, High Extent -3 Points, Low Extent -2 points and Very Low Extent – 1 point respectively. The instruments were validated by two experts in test and measurement while the reliability was determined using Cronbach Method. The following reliability indexes are: .83 for Managing National Social Investment Programmes and .86 for Economic Sustainability in Education. The sub scales are National cash transfer programme .82, Job creation programme .84, Empowerment programme .82 and National home-grown school feeding programme .86 accordingly. The research questionnaire was administered by the researcher and with the help of two assistance. Out of 313 copies of questionnaire administered, 304 were properly retrieved which represented 96% success rate. The research questions were answered using simple regression while the hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with simple regression at 0.05 level of significant. Tables were constructed with respect of various research questions and hypotheses. The SPSS was adopted for the analysis.

Result

Research Question 1: To what extent does national cash transfer programme predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be .477 while the regression squared value was computed to be .229. This shows that there is a prediction between national cash transfer programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that national cash transfer programme predicted economic sustainability by 22.9% while the remaining 77.1% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.

Table 1. Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which National Cash Transfer Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Remarks
1	.477	.229	.152	22.9% prediction

Research Question 2: To what extent does job creation programme predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be .422 while the regression squared value was computed to be .178. This shows that there is a prediction between job creation programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that job creation programme predicted economic sustainability by 17.8% while the remaining 82.2% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.

Table 2. Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Job Creation Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Remark
1	.422	.178	.183	17.8% prediction

Research Question 3: To what extent does empowerment programme predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

Table 3 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be .394 while the regression squared value was computed to be .155. This shows that there is a prediction between empowerment programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that empowerment programme predicted economic sustainability by 15.5% while the remaining 84.5% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.

Table 3. Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Empowerment Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Remarks
1	.394	.155	.151	15.5% prediction

Research Question 4: To what extent does national home-grown school feeding programme predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State?

Table 4 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be .442 while the regression squared value was computed to be .195. This shows that there is a prediction between national home-grown school feeding programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that National home-grown school feeding programme predicted economic sustainability by 19.5% while the remaining 80.5% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.

Table 4. Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Remarks
1	.442	.195	.071	19.5% prediction

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: National cash transfer programme does not significantly predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 5 revealed that national cash transfer programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State by .477. The t-test value 2.372 associated with simple regression was statistically significant at .000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, there is a significant prediction between national cash transfer programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 5. T-Test Associated with Simple Regression on Extent National Cash Transfer Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	35.307	.225		134.427	.000
	National cash transfer programme	.243	.010	.477	2.372	.114

Hypothesis 2: Job creation programme does not significantly predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 6 revealed that job creation programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State by .422. The t-test value 8.263 associated with simple regression was statistically significant at .000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, there is a significant prediction between job creation programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 6. T-Test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent to which Job Creation Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	25.720	1.362		18.882	.000
	Job creation programme	.303	.037	.422	8.263	.000

Hypothesis 3: Empowerment programme does not significantly predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 7 revealed that empowerment programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State by .934. The t-test value 2.833 associated with simple regression was statistically significant at .000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, there is a significant prediction between empowerment programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 7. T-Test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent to which Empowerment Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	33.568	1.651		29.141	.000
	Empowerment programme	.098	.013	.934	2.833	.005

Hypothesis 4: National home-grown school feeding programme does not significantly predict economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 8 revealed that National home-grown school feeding programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State by .472. The t-test value 6.715 associated with simple regression was statistically significant at .000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, there is a significant prediction between national home-grown school feeding programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Table 8. T-Test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent to which National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme Predict Economic Sustainability in Education in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	34.675	.891		43.543	.000
	National home-grown school feeding programme	.182	.072	.472	6.715	.000

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study are summarized as shown below:

1. National cash transfer programme predicted economic sustainability by 22.9% while the remaining 77.1% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.
2. Job creation programme predicted economic sustainability by 17.8% while the remaining 82.2% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.

3. Empowerment programme predicted economic sustainability by 15.5% while the remaining 84.5% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.
4. National home-grown school feeding programme predicted economic sustainability by 19.5% while the remaining 80.5% was accounted by other variables not investigated in this study.
5. There is a significant prediction between national cash transfer programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
6. There is a significant prediction between job creation programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
7. There is a significant prediction between empowerment programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.
8. There is a significant prediction between national home-grown school feeding programme and economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings is based on the followings:

1. National cash transfer programme and Economic sustainability
2. Job creation programme and Economic sustainability
3. Empowerment programme and Economic sustainability
4. National home-grown school feeding programme and Economic sustainability

National Cash Transfer Programme and Economic Sustainability

The first finding of the study revealed that national cash transfer programme predicted economic sustainability by 22.9% while the remaining 77.1% was accounted by other variables. This showed that national cash transfer programme to an extent predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. In line with the findings of this study, Akujuru (2019) submitted that cash transfer is the preparation for positive occupation to enhance specific skills which is job or task oriented rather than personal.

Bisong (2019) submitted, the cash transfer is a development aimed at developing business competence such as technical, human conceptual and managerial for furtherance of individual and organizational growth. Therefore, the result of the hypothesis revealed that national cash transfer programme significantly predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Job Creation Programme and Economic Sustainability

The second finding of this study revealed that job creation programme predicted economic sustainability by 17.8% while the remaining 82.2% was accounted by other variables. This indicates that job creation programme account for 17.8% of economic sustainability. This to an extent indicated that job creation programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. This is in consonance with the findings of Buunk, and Castro Solano, (2010). that any job creation is organization's performance system which should take into consideration the level of the service, which directly affects employee benefits policy and the sustainability of the service.

Job creation programme system is an important tool that management can use to channel employee motivation in desired ways. In other words, job creation programme systems seek to attract people to join the organization to keep them coming to work, and motivate them to perform to high levels. The findings of the hypothesis indicated that job creation programme significantly predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State (Abera, 2017).

Empowerment Programme and Economic Sustainability

The third finding of this study revealed that empowerment programme predicted economic sustainability by 15.5% while the remaining 84.5% was accounted by other variables. This indicates to an extent that empowerment programme predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State. This is in relation to Awojobi (2019), empowerment programme is a formal event to improve economic development, which has clearly stated performance dimensions and/or criteria that are used in the evaluation process. The result from the hypothesis showed that empowerment programme significantly predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme and Economic Sustainability

The findings of the study revealed that National home-grown school feeding programme predicted economic sustainability by 19.5% while the remaining 80.5% was accounted by other variables. This implies that to an extent the national home-grown school feeding programme plays an important role in determining economic sustainability. This is in consonance with the findings of Ugo (2018) who saw that national home-grown school feeding programme as an upward way to growth and job elevation with better status, higher responsibility and higher pay. Findings from the fourth hypothesis of this study revealed that national home-grown school feeding programme significantly predicted economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Conclusion

The study has shown that all the components of managing national social investment programmes practices which are considered in this study has positive predictions to economic sustainability in education in Rivers State with different determinism. The argument is that if they are contributing factors, there is need for secondary school managers to improve in their responsibilities for better economic sustainability in education in Rivers State.

Recommendations

The following are hereby recommended:

- 1) Government should improve on national cash transfer programme for her citizens to ensure economic sustainability.
- 2) Job creation programme should be a point of consideration especially for those who exceptionally don't have job for economic sustainability.
- 3) Empowerment programme should be looked into, especially for youth who have for economic sustainability.

4) Administrators should consider home-grown school feeding as strategy to improve economic sustainability.

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